

New Population Policy of Uttar Pradesh : A Socio-Economic Evaluation

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ABSTRACT

Recently, the draft of a new population policy was released by the Uttar Pradesh government. Its objective is to achieve the target of population stabilization in Uttar Pradesh by various incentives and punitive measures so that the Total Fertility Rate (TFR) can be brought to the replacement level of 2.1. Although the total fertility rate is declining rapidly in Uttar Pradesh, the new population policy is very relevant to achieve the goal of population stabilization by 2030 as per the goals declared by the United Nations. But the evaluation of any population policy should not be aimed only at reducing the population. Population policy should be evaluated keeping in view the poverty, inequality, health and safety of women etc. The punitive aspect inherent in the population policy of Uttar Pradesh is similar to the Chinese model, but any strategy related to population in India should be based on people's choice as India is the largest democracy in the world. The experience of South Indian states shows that economic development as well as emphasis on education, health and women empowerment is far better than punitive measures. A rigid and restrictive population policy can lead to problems like female feticide, unsafe abortion, female Divorce, segregation of poor and marginalized people from government schemes. However, in the new population policy, provisions have been made by the government to strengthen public health facilities, make proper arrangements for safe abortion, increase the supply of contraceptive means and make the public aware.

INTRODUCTION

The population of any country is the human asset of this country. The economic development of any country depends not only on physical resources but also on human resources. Population is a form of human resource which is very essential for economic development because human resources are also necessary for economic development along with capital and material resources. But when the population becomes more in comparison to the natural resources, that is, the population exceeds the optimum proportion, then the problem of overpopulation arises. This is the situation in Uttar Pradesh at present. Uttar Pradesh is the most populous state of India in absolute terms, whereas in terms of population growth rate, in relative terms, Uttar Pradesh ranks fifteenth in India. The problem of population in Uttar Pradesh becomes more serious because while on one hand the population of Uttar Pradesh is 16.50 percent of the total population of India, on the other hand the area of Uttar Pradesh is 7.3 percent of the total area of India. This is the reason that in terms of population density, Uttar Pradesh ranks fourth in India after Bihar, Bengal and Kerala. The total fertility rate in Uttar Pradesh is 2.7 while the national average is 2.1. As per NFHS-4(2015-16) data, 11 states in India had the Total Fertility Rate (TFR) replacement level more than 2.1. Uttar Pradesh was ranked third in terms of high fertility rate among these 11 states. In such a situation the need for a new population policy was being felt strongly in Uttar Pradesh. The population of any country is closely related to the socio-economic conditions of that country. In such a situation, it is necessary that the new population policy of Uttar Pradesh should be seen in the socio-economic scenario of Uttar Pradesh.

AIM OF THE STUDY:

- 1- What is the relevance of the new population policy of Uttar Pradesh at present.
- 2- Study of the impact of the new population policy of Uttar Pradesh on women.
- 3- Study of the new population policy in the context of poverty, unemployment and malnutrition prevailing in Uttar Pradesh.
- 4- Comparison of the new population policy of Uttar Pradesh with the population policy of other states of India and China.

NEW POPULATION POLICY OF UTTAR PRADESH:

The draft of a new population policy for Uttar Pradesh has been issued by the Government of Uttar Pradesh through "The Uttar Pradesh Population (Control, Stabilization and Welfare) Bill, 2021" which will be for the year 2021 to 2030. In this draft, a target has been set to bring the Gross Fertility Rate in Uttar Pradesh to 2.1 by the year 2026 and to 1.9 by the year 2030. To achieve this goal, the following provisions have been made in this policy.

- Increase Modern Contraceptive Prevalence Rate from 31.7 to 45 by 2026 and 52 by 2030; increase male methods of contraception use from 10.8 to 15.1 by 2026 and 16.4 by 2030;
- Decrease Maternal Mortality Rate from 197 to 150 to 98 and Infant Mortality Rate from 43 to 32 to 22 and Under 5 Infant Mortality Rate from 47 to 35 to 25
- The State's policy also aims at increasing the life expectancy from 64.3 to 69 by 2030 and child sex ratio (0-6 years) from 899 to 919 by 2030.
- In the new policy, the ration card of a person having more than two children will be limited to four members and he will not be eligible to receive any kind of government subsidy.
- Within a year of the implementation of the law, all government employees and public representatives elected in the local body elections will have to give an affidavit that they will not violate the rule. If they give birth to a third child after giving the affidavit, then the draft has recommended stopping promotion and even dismissal of government employees. However, there is no bar on the adoption of a third child.
- The government will give special facilities to the parents who follow the policy of two children and have voluntary sterilization.
- Such government employees will get many facilities like two extra salary increment, promotion, 12 months maternity or paternity leave, insurance coverage for spouse, exemption in government housing schemes, increase in employer contribution in PF.
- Those who do not have government jobs, in the draft, it is proposed to provide many facilities like water, electricity, home tax, home loan.
- A person with more than two children will not get the benefit of government schemes. That person will not be able to apply for a government job or contest the election of any local body.
- In the new population policy of Uttar Pradesh, not only the responsibility of the citizens has been fixed but the responsibilities of the state have also been fixed. The government will increase the supply of contraceptive means under family planning programs and make proper arrangements for safe abortion. Along with this, health facilities will increase through ATM, teleconsultancy, shagun kit etc. which can help in reducing infant mortality rate and maternal mortality rate.
- Uttar Pradesh's new population policy is being described as a step towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals announced by the United Nations by 2030.

NEW POPULATION POLICY OF UTTAR PRADESH: AND PROBLEM OF OVERPOPULATION:

Certainly there has been a decline in the population growth rate of Uttar Pradesh in the last years, but it has been higher than the average population growth rate of the whole of India and educationally and socially developed states. The average population growth rate of the whole of India started declining after the decade 1971-1981, that is, after the decade 1971-1981, India entered the third stage of the transition to the birth index.

In Uttar Pradesh this process has started after the decade 1991-2001. In 2001-2011, where the population growth rate of the whole of India was 17.70 percent, it was 20.23 percent in Uttar Pradesh. The new population policy of Uttar Pradesh should be seen in this perspective. Its objective is to achieve the goal of population stabilization by controlling population growth in the future. The need for a new population policy was being felt strongly in Uttar Pradesh. In the new population policy, a target has been set to bring the Gross Fertility Rate in Uttar Pradesh to 2.1 by 2026 and to 1.9 by 2030, which is a welcome step. However, Uttar Pradesh has performed exceptionally well in reducing the total fertility rate over the years. As per NFHS-3 (2005-06) data, TFR in Uttar Pradesh 3.8 which was reduced to 2.7 in NFHS-4 (2015-16). This means that on an average, a woman from Uttar Pradesh produced one less child. According to the data of NFHS-3 and NFHS-4, the total fertility rate of Uttar Pradesh has declined the most as compared to other states. It is expected that even without the new population policy, Uttar Pradesh will achieve the replacement level of total fertility rate by 2025. The development in the socio-economic sector of Uttar Pradesh in the last years has played an important role in controlling the population of Uttar Pradesh. The 1994 Conference on Population and Development in Cairo recognized that the solution of issues related to poverty and high fertility rates depended on factors such as the spread of public education, the empowerment of women, and improvements in maternal and child health. According to the theory of demographic transition, the rate of population growth of a country depends on the economic development of that country. The success of South Indian states in

controlling population growth shows that economic development as well as emphasis on education, health and women empowerment is far better than punitive measures. The results of the penal provisions adopted by the government for population control in 1975 were not positive, that is why no government after 1977 could muster the courage to include it in its manifesto. The punitive aspect related to the population policy of Uttar Pradesh is like the model of China but China is not a democratic country. India is the largest democracy in the world where any strategy related to population should be based on people's choice. According to Perianayagam Arokiasamy, Head, Department of Development Studies, International Institute for Population Science, Mumbai "The strategy has to be choice-based, so that people voluntarily decide to have fewer children because of access to education or maybe by giving them positive incentives,". According to Arokiasamy a better way of dealing with population control measures is a more efficient health system, access to contraception and greater awareness among people. Therefore, it is necessary that instead of punitive measures, emphasis should be given on incentives in the new population policy of Uttar Pradesh. It cannot be said that the population growth of Uttar Pradesh will stop with the new population policy of Uttar Pradesh. Uttar Pradesh is a young state with one third of its population being youth, so the population will continue to grow despite the decline in fertility. In demography this is called "population dynamics". According to the new population policy, people will have to present a certificate related to sterilization to get the benefits of government schemes. With this it is possible that people produce both their children at short time intervals, as a result of the new population policy, the population can increase rapidly in the short run. Population should not be seen as a problem in any policy related to population. Issues like "Denial dividend" must be included in population related policies. Uttar Pradesh is a young state where by skilling and training the population, it can be transformed into human resource, which will be helpful in the economic development of Uttar Pradesh. According to the recently released Skill Development Report-2021, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh are the top three states with the highest employable talent. Therefore, along with implementing the population policy, the Uttar Pradesh government should also pay attention to Human Resource Management. Along with implementing the new population policy, the Chinese model of population control should also be taken into account. China implemented the "one child policy" in 1979 to deal with the growing population, but due to this policy, the share of people over 65 years of age in the total population of China increased from 13.26 percent in 2010 to 18.70 percent in 2020.

POVERTY, INEQUALITY AND NEW POPULATION POLICY:

On the one hand, where there is poverty, the reason for excessive population, on the other hand, the reason for poverty is also excessive population. Poverty and population are closely related to each other. The reason for inequality is also the excessive population. A poor family produces more children because in such a family the children are considered as the source of future income. Often in poor families, the son is considered a stick of old age, so in the desire of more sons, the poor family produces more children and then again he gets caught in the vicious circle of poverty. The new population policy released by the Government of Uttar Pradesh breaks this vicious circle and compels the poor family to adopt the norm of two children through its punitive and incentive measures. Therefore, the goal of the new population policy of Uttar Pradesh is to achieve poverty alleviation and population control simultaneously. But the following points should be noted in the context of this policy.

- Areas with high poverty, low economic development and less educated women tend to have higher levels of fertility. According to the NFHS-4 data, the TFR level in women aged 15 to 49 years in Uttar Pradesh was 3.52 among women who were out of school, while the TFR level was 1.88 in women with 12 or more schooling. Kerala, Tamil Nadu/Himachal Pradesh and Andhra Pradesh were among the top three states in the SDG India Index 2020-21, developed by NITI Aayog in collaboration with the United Nations, with the TFR replacement level below 2.1 in all these states.
- The data clearly shows that it is the poor who vote most enthusiastically in the hope that they will find a government that will support their needs. According to Perianayagam Arokiasamy, Head, Department of Development Studies, International Institute for Population Science, Mumbai "De-incentivisation, such as taking away subsidies, will only focus on a very small portion of people. Only a small percentage of people get subsidies," According to Arokiasamy, it is also unfair to stop poor people from government schemes if they have more than two children. Sometimes, it is because of extreme poverty, lack of awareness or inability to afford contraceptives or abortion that people have more children. They said "They are already suffering, and will suffer even more if their subsidy is taken away." Presently the total fertility rate in Uttar Pradesh is declining rapidly. Aditya Kumar Singh, a public policy expert said "It shows the state has reached the next phase of demographic transition where population growth is set to slow down in next two decades,". Poonam Muttreja, executive director of Population Foundation of India, said: "UP has the second-highest fertility rate in India and it has recorded the largest decrease in Total Fertility Rate." In such a situation, it is more necessary that the efforts to reduce poverty in Uttar Pradesh should be accelerated so that poor families can adopt the norm of two children voluntarily and of their choice. Any punitive population policy can deprive the poor and marginalized people of massive government benefits. After the corona virus epidemic, the dependence of poor families on government schemes has increased,

in such a situation it is not appropriate to deprive the families of two children from the government subsidy. After the corona virus epidemic, the dependence of poor families on government schemes has increased, in such a situation it is not appropriate to deprive the families of two children from the government subsidy. In the 1990s and 2000s, the incentive and punitive policies adopted by many states like Haryana, undivided Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Chhattisgarh, Odisha to control the population were condemned by the National Human Rights Commission. Depriving them of the welfare schemes made for the poor themselves will further increase their poverty and consequently they will be forced to have more children. Sometimes the poor themselves are not the cause of their poverty. Sometimes government schemes do not reach the poor due to lapses and commissions in government schemes. When a poor family produces more children due to its poverty then we cannot say that it is itself responsible for it. Therefore, punishing them for their lapses and commissions by the government is tantamount to punishing them for their poverty and the sins of others.

- Depriving a family of more than two children from municipal elections is also undemocratic. Because in a healthy political democratic system, voters should have maximum choice and there should be no restriction on their political choice. The system of local body elections was introduced by the constitution to connect the poor and the deprived with the Indian democracy so that people of this class could be brought in the main stream of development. The new population policy of Uttar Pradesh has to respect these sentiments of the Constitution. Municipal elections are already dominated by money power and muscle power, so keeping the poor and downtrodden out of it is not democratic in any way. If this law is made, the poor people who are eligible to stand as candidates will be greatly reduced and democracy will face further contraction.
- It is also wrong to argue that controlling population will increase the base of natural resources. It is more important in this context to review the consumption pattern. At present, the main cause of environmental pollution is indulgent and convenient lifestyle. This indulgent culture causes the rich to consume more natural resources and contribute more to greenhouse gas emissions than the poor.
- The new population policy prohibits those who have more than two children from taking up government jobs. This will hurt the members of the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribe communities the most, they will be deprived of the right of reservation in a large number of government jobs. According to the NFHS-4 (2015-16) data, the total fertility rate among Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes in Uttar Pradesh was 3.09 and 3.61, while it was 2.76 and 2.28 for Other Backward Classes and Others.

NEW POPULATION POLICY AND WOMEN:

Any population policy should be evaluated in the context of women's health, security and socio-economic rights. One of the main reasons for the high maternal mortality rate in Uttar Pradesh is the relatively high total fertility rate. When a woman produces more children, it has a negative effect on the health of the woman, which sometimes becomes the cause of her death. The maternal mortality rate in Uttar Pradesh was 258 in 2016 as compared to the national average of 178. At present, the maternal mortality rate in Uttar Pradesh is 197 as against the national average of 113. In the new population policy, a target has been set to bring down the maternal mortality rate from the present 197 to 150 by 2026 and to 98 by 2030.

Controlling the population by the new population policy will definitely have a favorable effect on the health of women and there will be a decline in the maternal mortality rate in Uttar Pradesh. Along with maternal mortality rate, infant mortality rate in Uttar Pradesh is also higher than the national average. Five years ago, the IMR was 53 while the national average was 42. Today, it stands at 43 against the national average of 33. In the new population policy, a target has been set to reduce the infant mortality rate from 43 to 32 by 2026 and to 22 by 2030. One of the main reasons for the high total fertility rate in Uttar Pradesh is the high infant mortality rate. A woman deliberately produces more children, so that even if some of her children die, some of her children may still live. Therefore, to control the population growth, it is necessary to reduce the infant mortality rate. Therefore, the new population policy will prove to be very beneficial for women because now women will have to produce less children on average than before. But according to some scholars, the new population policy can also adversely affect the health of women and their marital status. like---

- Indian society is a patriarchal society where the burden of sterilization is often borne by women. Almost two-fifths (38%) of men age 15-49 in Uttar Pradesh agree that contraception is women's business and a man should not have to worry about it, according to NFHS-4 (2015-16) data. According to NFHS-4(2015-16) data, the percentage of sterilization under contraceptive measures in Uttar Pradesh is 17.1 percent, in which the percentage of male sterilization is only 0.1%. Under the new population policy, if a couple opts for sterilization after having one child, they will be given financial assistance by the government. If the child is a daughter, then one lakh, if there is a son, then the financial help of 80 thousand will be given by the government. Therefore, there is every possibility that most of the women will opt for sterilization putting their health and safety at risk. According to the NFHS-4(2015-16) data, 88 percent of the women who undergo vasectomy are dependent on public health facilities like CHC, PHC, Rural Hospital, Municipal Hospital etc. for sterilization. Therefore, with the implementation of the new

population policy, public health facilities will have to be strengthened. This is the reason why in the new population policy, emphasis has been laid on promoting sterilization through improved health facilities, increasing the accessibility of contraceptive measures, making proper arrangements for safe abortion, easy solution to the problem of impotence/infertility etc.

- India is one of the countries with high female feticide. According to the United Nations, an estimated 2,000 births of girl child are illegally aborted in India every day. According to a UNICEF report, about 50 million girls and women are missing from India's population due to systematic gender discrimination in India. 60 million girls have gone missing due to China's one child policy. In Indian society, the son is considered the stick of old age, which is the future source of livelihood of the family. Therefore, the size of the family usually increases due to the preference given to the birth of boys over girls. This is one of the main reasons for the high total fertility rate in Uttar Pradesh. Therefore, it is natural for the new population policy to have problems like female feticide and unsafe abortion. Economists Abhishek Chakraborty and S Anukreethy, in their 2017 paper, "Democracy and Demography: Social Effects of Fertility Limits on Local Leaders," noted that population control measures can worsen the sex ratio at birth-Because of Indian society's preference for male children.
- With the implementation of the new population policy, there is every possibility of a woman getting divorced if the child is a girl or the death of the child, in which case the woman may have to face a very uncertain future as she would have been sterilised. According to NFHS-4 (2015-16) data, 80 percent of couples want at least one boy. There are innumerable cases of women in India facing domestic violence, divorce and death because they gave birth to a girl child. Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Odisha and Assam already have a two-child policy. A study conducted in 2005 found an increase in the incidence of unsafe sex-selective abortions (female feticide), men separating or divorcing their wives, and giving up children for adoption with the intention of contesting elections in these states.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the new population policy of Uttar Pradesh is an important step taken to control the population of India's most populous state in future.

The Total Fertility Rate (TFR) in Uttar Pradesh is rapidly rising to the replacement level of 2.1. Certainly the new population policy will accelerate this process and social consciousness will be spread among the people towards the ideal of "we do our two". No policy is perfect, every policy has some positive side and some negative side also. What is needed is that its negative aspects are minimized. Any policy related to population in India should be in accordance with the democratic tradition of India. Instead of punitive measures, the emphasis should be on incentives. The population of any country is strongly related to the socio-economic development of that country, South Indian states are examples of this. Therefore, along with economic development, issues such as the spread of public education, an efficient health system, access to contraceptives, women's empowerment and public awareness will also have to be given due attention. Population should not always be seen as a problem, issues like population dividend should also be taken into account. For this it is necessary that the programs related to skill development are implemented effectively.

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